

Research Article

Prototype FunLastic: Eco-Friendly LDPE Plastic with pH-Sensitive Fungal *Aspergillus niger* Encapsulation System

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Abstract: Low-Density Polyethylene (LDPE) waste is a type of plastic that is difficult to degrade and contributes to environmental pollution. Without proper intervention, LDPE waste is projected to reach 35.4 million metric tons by 2032. This study aimed to develop an environmentally friendly LDPE plastic system through an innovation called FunLastic (Fungi Plastic), which embeds pH-sensitive capsules containing *Aspergillus niger* spores within the plastic layer for controlled biodegradation. The innovation was developed through data analysis and prototyping. Based on secondary data, *A. niger* activity can reduce LDPE plastic mass by 4.41% in 28 days. Under laboratory conditions with 100% active spores, 1 gram of LDPE plastic degrades in ± 1.8 years. With 50% spore effectiveness due to external factors, degradation takes ± 3.5 years. Capsules were produced using ionotropic gelation with 2% sodium alginate and 0.1 M calcium chloride (CaCl_2), yielding stable 2–4 mm capsules. Each capsule contained approximately 1.4×10^5 spores; eight capsules were used per treatment, totaling $\pm 1.12 \times 10^6$ spores. Spore release followed the Korsmeyer–Peppas model, beginning on day 3 and ending by day 10 under moist soil with pH 5–6. The controlled release system prevents mold overgrowth and maintains biodegradation effectiveness. FunLastic is designed as a degradable LDPE plastic alternative that preserves its mechanical strength during initial use while addressing plastic pollution through a self-activated, scientifically validated approach.

Keywords: *Aspergillus niger*; ionotropic gelation; Korsmeyer–Peppas; LDPE; pH-sensitive encapsulation; plastic biodegradation.

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1. INTRODUCTION

A lot of plastic consumption which cannot be decomposed still have been one of the problems that world must face. Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development said that globally, it is estimated that leakage of plastics to the environment will double to 44 million tons per year. Moreover, the accumulation of plastics in the lakes, rivers, and oceans is projected to increase threefold. This is due to the surge in plastic waste, which is expected to increase from 353 million tons in 2019 to 1,014 million tons in 2060. Currently, the Center for Biological Diversity states that the world uses 5 trillion plastic bags every year. It should be noted that decomposing plastics in landfills takes 1,000 years. Then, it will be decomposed into microplastics that absorb toxins so that they can pollute the environment.

One type of plastics that commonly found daily is LDPE (Low-Density Polyethylene). The main ingredient of LDPE is ethylene (C_2H_4) which through a high-pressure polymerization process produces a low-density polyethylene structure. The reason LDPE is often used is because one type of plastics that

has a branched molecular structure makes the plastic more flexible and resistant to moisture than other polyethylenes such as HDPE (High-Density Polyethylene). However, LDPE plastic is not free from the drawback of plastic packaging in general. It is difficult to decompose naturally. An example of the use of LDPE plastics can be found in plastic bags. Data from 2022 indicates that Asia Pacific is the largest consumer of LDPE with a market share of around 46%. The global LDPE market is expected to grow at a CAGR (Compounded annual growth rate) of 4.5% during the period 2023 to 2032 and can reach almost 35.4 million metric tons in 2032. Besides, applications in packaging contribute almost 55% of total consumption.

In 2018, LDPE contributed 14.9% of total global plastic waste. LDPE contributes significantly to the accumulation of plastic waste in the environment because it is difficult to decompose naturally. One of the negative impacts of LDPE pollution is damaging the life of the ecosystem of living things. The use of LDPE plastic is one of the focuses of SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals) number 12 which reads "Responsible Consumption and Production". The name of the product to be designed is FunLastic which is an abbreviation of Fungi Plastik. The existence of this project can also meet the main targets and indicators of SDGs 12, namely managing natural resources sustainably (12.2), managing chemicals and waste in an environmentally friendly manner (12.4), significantly reducing the amount of waste (12.5), and increasing public awareness of a sustainable lifestyle and harmony with nature (12.8). Based on data from the Asia Pacific and Indonesia targets, indicators 12.4 and 12.5 have progressed to reach yellow, which means they have low-intensity challenges (progress below 50%) in achieving green. Indicator 12.2 shows red, which means there are serious challenges in realizing it. Indicator 12.8 has not yet received data related to the fulfillment of the indicator or is usually marked with gray.

In order to achieve the SDGs target, especially number 12, global efforts are needed in developing LDPE plastic to make it easier to decompose. Various methods have been developed, especially in accelerating plastic degradation involving microorganisms such as bacteria and fungi as the main decomposers. The *Aspergillus niger* has been proven to be able to degrade certain plastics under certain conditions. However, there is a major challenge in implementing this innovation. How we ensure that the fungus is only active in a suitable environment for degradation and the effectiveness of the fungus can be in the plastic itself. Therefore, the concept of pH-sensitive encapsulation is used to overcome this. LDPE plastic can be decomposed because it has undergone innovation using pH-sensitive *Aspergillus niger* fungus encapsulation, with *Aspergillus niger* fungus as a trigger so that it can decompose in a shorter time. That is the reason why this product is named FunLastic. The concept of pH-sensitive encapsulation was developed by providing fungal spores packaged in capsules that only break at a certain pH. With this approach, the fungus remains inactive during the use of the plastic and begins to work when the plastic waste is in an environment that supports the biodegradation process. This innovation aims to create innovative solutions that can build a better future in the field of environmental sustainability. Through the selection of the right materials, this method has the potential to be a more effective alternative than plastic in general.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

2.1 Method and Materials of the Study

The method used in the study is a data analysis approach and data-based simulation to apply the potential for biodegradation of LDPE plastic that has been modified with a pH-sensitive fungal encapsulation system. The data were obtained from previous studies on plastic degradation by *Aspergillus niger*, suitable pH-sensitive encapsulation content, and environmental factors that affect its effectiveness. *Aspergillus niger* degradation and pH-sensitive capsule content were used in data-based simulations in plastic modelling rather than in laboratory experiments. The duration of the fungal degradation process was taken by research conducted on Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) media which

has guaranteed sterility, humidity, and no external factors such as temperature, light, and weather. Therefore, if the fungus decomposed in the soil, the effectiveness was not 100% and calculations were carried out by considering the effectiveness of soil conditions (50-80%) although it used the same method. The capsule release time was calculated from the first to the tenth day using the Korsmeyer-Peppas method. In this case, the study did not conduct direct tests in the laboratory but used previous data and new innovations to make estimates of the plastic degradation process by fungi in the form of data.

2.2 pH-Sensitive Encapsulation Prototype and Procedure

Figure 1. pH-Sensitive Encapsulation Prototype.

Encapsulation pH-Sensitive Procedure:

1. Grow *Aspergillus niger* on PDA media for 5-7 days at room temperature (25-30°C). Pour 10 mL of sterile distilled water onto the surface of the media and shake gently to release the spores. Calculate the spore density using a hemocytometer to achieve the initial target.
2. Dissolve 2 grams of sodium alginate into 100 mL of sterile distilled water and stir using a magnetic stirrer or blender until homogeneous and thick. Pour the spore solution into the alginate solution and stir slowly.
3. Dissolve 1.11 grams of $CaCl_2$ in 100 mL of sterile distilled water to form a 0.1M $CaCl_2$ solution.
4. Put the alginate and spore solutions into a pipette, drop them slowly into the 0.1 M $CaCl_2$ solution which will immediately form gel granules/capsules. Let stand for 30 minutes for the capsules to harden completely. Filter the capsules and wash lightly with sterile distilled water to remove excess calcium ions.
5. Dry at room temperature for 24-48 hours or at low temperature (40-45°C) for 6-8 hours for longer-lasting capsules.

2.3 FunLastic Prototype and Manufacturing Procedure

FunLastic Making Procedure:

1. Preparation of Materials and Tools
 Materials: LDPE (resin or pellets) ± 5 gr, *Aspergillus niger* spore encapsulation capsules, plasticizer (glycerol or PEG). Tools: heat-resistant container, hot plate or low-temperature oven, heat-resistant flat mold.

2. **LDPE Melting**
Put the LDPE pellets into a heat-resistant container. Heat on a hot plate or oven at 110-130°C slowly until the LDPE melts (temperature must be no more than 135°C to maintain the capsule structure).
3. **Adding Encapsulation Capsules**
After the LDPE melts like a thick paste, remove from heat. Let the temperature drop slightly to around 60-70°C so that the capsules are not immediately damaged when mixed. Sprinkle the capsules onto the surface of the liquid plastic. Pour a thin layer of melted LDPE to cover the capsules.
4. **Forming and Cooling**
Pour the plastic mixture that already contains the capsules. Then, spread with a metal spatula. Let it hard at room temperature for ±15-30 minutes.
Once the plastic has hardened, remove it from the mold. The plastic is ready to use.

Figure 2. Prototype FunLastic.

3. FINDINGS

3.1 LDPE plastic content

LDPE is a plastic with code number 4 which is a type of plastic that is difficult to decompose and is the most widely used in the world. LDPE is hydrophobic so that microorganisms are difficult to attach and decompose without external factors. LDPE plastic has a polymer chemical structure content that is easy to produce. LDPE plastic polymers have fairly long and numerous branch chains. The density of LDPE plastic ranges from 0.91-0.94/cm and has loose molecules that make it elastic and transparent. The thermoplastic used consists of polyethylene (PE) which consists of a long chain of ethylene monomers, polypropylene (PP) and polystyrene (PS) which are composed of the polymerization process of ethane molecules C_2H_4 ($CH_2 = CH_2$) to form double bonds. *Aspergillus niger* can produce oxidative enzymes (such as peroxidase and laccase) which can break down the LDP carbon chain gradually.

3.2 Plastic Biodegradation by *Aspergillus niger*

Aspergillus niger has extracellular enzymes that can decompose organic materials. Lignin peroxidase (Lip), manganese peroxidase (MnP), and laccase enzymes are enzymes released by the *Aspergillus niger* when helping the biodegradation process. Fungi have great potential as LDPE degrading agents, thanks to their ability to produce extracellular enzymes that can break down complex

LDPE polymers (Alshehrei, 2017). This process allows for effective degradation, producing hydrophobin and chaplin proteins that function as surfactants. This content helps reduce the hydrophobicity of the polymer, thereby increasing the efficiency of the degradation process. The reason using *Aspergillus niger* compared to other microorganisms is that fungi are known to have high diversity and more varied metabolic abilities compared to bacteria (Sen and Raut, 2015). Fungal enzymes can also penetrate the porous structure of plastic, increase cracks and pores, thereby accelerating degradation (Temporiti, M. E. E. et al., 2022). The ability of *Aspergillus niger* to penetrate and spread hyphae into plastic in a targeted manner quickly and widely in the LDPE degradation process is an advantage over other microbes (Sáenz, M. et al., 2019). External factors that affect the effectiveness of the degradation process include soil pH, soil moisture, temperature, microbial competitors, nutrient adequacy, and soil aeration.

3.3 Encapsulation of Fungus using pH-Sensitive Materials

Encapsulation is a process to maintain the original properties of a material using coating material. The encapsulation method used is ionotropic gelation, which is the formation of capsules through ionic reactions. The role of encapsulation in the project design is to make it easier to handle active ingredients and allow for controlled release. Protecting fungal spores under normal conditions and decomposing when pH conditions are acidic, must have pH-sensitive encapsulation properties. The main encapsulation layer consists of alginate and calcium chloride as an encapsulation matrix for *Aspergillus niger* which will be stable if at natural pH conditions and can decompose under low Ca²⁺-or acidic pH conditions. The content required for the pH-sensitive layer is chitosan and polyaniline. Chitosan is known to be soluble in acidic conditions and is often used in controlled release of microbes. Polyaniline is used to achieve the properties of changes in conductivity and solubility according to the pH of the food environment. Additional stabilizers, such as gum arabic powder, are needed to improve the distribution of fungi in the capsule so that they do not clump. (Zouhair, S. et al., 2017) stated that the optimal pH for the growth of *Aspergillus niger* is in the range of 4 to 6.5. The Korsmeyer-Peppas model is a mathematical model used for the release mechanism of active substances (fungal spores) from a polymer system (for example, alginate-based capsules). This method is used because mushroom capsules are based on natural polymers (alginate). The release their contents slowly. This model explains the combination of diffusion mechanisms as occurs in pH-sensitive capsules. This method has also been widely used in the field of microbial encapsulation and controlled release. Therefore, the encapsulation which will be made focuses on the release of fungi at an acidic pH so that the fungi can degrade LDPE plastic.

4. DISCUSSION

The data taken from the research by Suharpina, et al. (2021) who conducted degradation of LDPE plastic by *Aspergillus niger* inoculated into Erlenmeyer flasks contained molasses media and also LDPE plastic measuring 1 × 1 cm and weighing 1 gram. The data that has been displayed shows the research on Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) media which has guaranteed sterility, humidity, and no external factors that affect such as temperature, light, and weather. Then, the Erlenmeyer flask was incubated for 4 weeks placed in a shaker along with the population calculation. Population calculations were carried out at dilutions of 10⁻⁵ and 10⁻⁵ using the total plate count method before being put into the carrier material. The reduction in LDPE plastic levels carried out by *Aspergillus niger* for 4 weeks was 4.41%.

Figure 3. Suharpina, et al.: Graph of LDPE Plastic Mass Reduction on PDA Media.

The data shows a reduction in plastic levels from week to week. The first week showed a decrease of 0.9953. In the second week it decreased to 0.95% or 0.9905. In the third week it continued to decrease 1.93% until 4.41% in the fourth week. The decrease LDPE plastic content in the fourth week was 0.9559. Therefore, the following calculation is use to use up the LDPE plastic content:

Median degradation rate from 0 MSI to 4 MSI

$$\frac{4.41\%}{4} = 1,1025\% \text{ per MSI}$$

To get 100% degradation:

$$\frac{100\%}{1,025\%} \text{ per MSI} = 90,7 \text{ MSI}$$

$$90,7 \times 1 \text{ week} = 90,7 \text{ weeks}$$

$$90,7 \times 7 = 635 \text{ days } (\pm 1,7 \text{ years})$$

It happened because the fungus secretes extracellular enzymes that break down plastic polymers into simpler forms. Enzymes that have a role in the process include laccase, lignin, peroxidase, manganese peroxidase, and versatile peroxidase. LDPE plastic is used as a carbon source for fungal metabolism. *Aspergillus niger* secretes enzymes that can oxidize LDPE which can make the plastic structure more brittle and decompose. The proteins produced by fungi are hydrophobin and chaplin as surfactants to reduce the hydrophobic properties of plastic and increase the rate of degradation. The long polymer structure of LDPE functions as a place for fungal attachment. It helps enzymes penetrate the pore structure of the plastic, enlarge the pores, and trigger cracks. The fungal activity in the degradation of LDPE plastic increases in the second week by 55% and 56% in the fourth week (Suharpina, et al., 2021).

The calculation may also change in real conditions because it depends on environmental factors such as pH, temperature, humidity, and fungal growth. Fungi can also cause a decrease in the pH of the media by up to 20% from its initial pH. It means that if the initial pH of the media is 5, then the pH can drop to around 4 due to fungal activity. Therefore, fungi are able to create more acidic conditions during the plastic degradation process. Suharpina, et al. (2021) stated that degradation process is

supported by the ideal pH which is acidic in the range of 4.5-5.6 based on laboratory research. He also said that *Aspergillus niger* began to show significant degradation of *Aspergillus niger* on the 5th day.

The data that has been displayed shows research on Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) media which has guaranteed the sterility, humidity, and no external factors that affect such as temperature, light, and weather. Therefore, although the method is the same, if the fungus decomposes in the soil, its effectiveness is not 100% due to the presence of other microbes in the soil, humidity, temperature, light, and humidity. The following is a table of the effect of the percentage effectiveness and the results of calculating the effectiveness of *Aspergillus niger* in the process of plastic degradation in the soil.

Table 1. Detailed Table of the Effect of the Effectiveness of the Degradation Process on Soil

Environmental Condition	Optimal Condition (80% Effectiveness)	Fair Condition (Effectiveness 60-70%)	Bad Condition (50% Effectiveness)
Soil pH	5-6.5	4.5-5.5/6.5-7.5	<4 or >8
Soil Moisture	60-70%	40-60%	<40% RH (dry)
Temperature	Stable 28-30°C	Mild day-night fluctuations (20-35°C)	Extreme fluctuations or <20°C day /<°C night
Microbial Competitors	Few (sterile/semi-sterile soil/fresh compost)	Medium (normal soil)	Lots (old landfill soil, lots of bacteria, 10 wild fungi)
Nutritional Adequacy	High (organic waste/compost added)	Sufficient (little organic residue)	Low (barren/hard ground)
Soil Aeration	Loose, porous, abundant, oxygen	Medium	Dense, partially anaerobic

Table 2. Calculation Table of Effectiveness of Degradation Process in Soil

The Effectiveness	Effective Degradation Rate	Estimated Days for 100% Degradation	Period
100%	4,41% per 28 days	±635 days	±1 year 8 months
80%	3,53% per 28 days	±794 days	±2 year 2 months
70%	3,09% per 28 days	±906 days	±2 year 5 months
60%	2,65% per 28 days	±1057 days	±2 year 9 months
50%	2,20% per 28 days	±1272 days	±3 year 5 months

The table shows that if the effectiveness of degradation by fungi is only 50%, plastic will still be able to decompose within a time span of ±3 years and 5 months. LDPE plastic was originally able to decompose within 1000 years. However, the innovation can provide a path of progress for every country to be able to use FunLastic.

The pH sensitive encapsulation was designed by using the ionotropic gelation method and a formula obtained from data-based analysis. The method is used because it does not require organic solvents or high temperatures and it only uses sodium alginate and *CaCl2* solutions which are expected to be more effective in packaging. Negative charged alginate reacts with calcium ions which can form a strong 3D gel network that is stable, insoluble in water, and resistant to light physical pressure. It

proves that even though there is a fungal content, the plastic bag also has strong resistance. The method helps protect spores from extreme environments and regulates the release of spores in moist soil conditions or marked by changes in environmental pH.

The method does not release all the mushrooms at once so that it can avoid overgrowth. The resulting capsules are round with a size of 2-4 mm containing mushroom spores. These capsules will be stable if they are in dry room temperature and can begin to decompose if they are in moist soil or acidic pH. 1 capsule contains $\pm 1,4 \cdot 10^5$ *Aspergillus niger* spores. The total spores needed to degrade 1 gram of LDPE plastic are around 106 spores, so 7-8 capsules are needed per 1 gram of plastic with a total of spores per treatment of $1.12 \cdot 10^6$.

The Korsmeyer-Peppas diffusion model is used to describe the release of active substances from polymeric systems, such as alginate capsules, and is stated by the equation:

$$\frac{M_t}{M_\infty} = k \cdot t^n$$

M_t = number of spores released at time t

M_∞ = total spores ($1,12 \times 10^6$)

t = day-

k = kinetic constant

n = diffusion exponent (assume 0.5 initially)

Assuming 90% of spores are released on day 7, this means:

$$\frac{M_t}{M_\infty} = 0,9 = k \cdot 7^{0.5}$$

$$0,9 = k \cdot \sqrt{7} = k \cdot 2,6458$$

$$k = \frac{0,9}{2,6458} \approx 0,340$$

Calculation M_t for $t = 1$ to $t = 10$:

Table 3. Percentage of *Aspergillus niger* Release.

Day-	Discharge percentage	Estimated active spores (from total $1,12 \times 10^6$)
1	34%	380.800
2	50%	560.000
3	65%	728.000
4	72%	806.400
5	8%	896.000
6	86%	963.200
7	90%	1.008.000
8	95%	1.064.000
9-10	100%	1.120.000

In wet soil conditions and pH 5-6, the capsules begin to release spores within 3-10 days depending on the sterility conditions and external factors of the soil media. After 9th day and above, the release is almost complete so it is considered saturated and there is no further release from the capsules. When the capsules enter a moist soil environment with a low pH, the ionotropic gel structure of the molecule breaks and the *Aspergillus niger* spores inside are slowly released naturally. The process mimics a biological response and does not require human intervention. The results of the effectiveness include water resistance because this plastic will dissolve at pH > 6 in the short term. The degradation of the plastic can also be done without a complicated process, simply by placing it in wet soil, landfill, or high organic soil that has an acidic pH. The release process is triggered by water diffusion into the alginate matrix, ion exchange, when calcium is displaced by Na^+/K^+ ions from the soil, and microbial or soil enzyme degradation. The gradual release is in accordance with the strategy to increase effectiveness and prevent overgrowth of spores.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the data analysis and prototypes that have been showed, it has shown the effectiveness of the presence of *Aspergillus niger* fungus in the manufacture of LDPE plastic so that the plastics can be decomposed. However, it needs to be reviewed that this research was not carried out directly. All calculations and simulations based on scientific data are expected to provide a real contribution to the development of LDPE plastic in the world. The results, if influenced by the effectiveness of environmental conditions by 50-100%, will also have an effect on the duration of plastic degradation. The release of fungal spores takes a long time for plastic degradation in the range of ± 1 year 8 months to 3 years 5 months. The innovation shows that plastic, which has been a world problem, can be minimized by the presence of FunLastic. Initially, LDPE plastic could decompose for 1000 years, but if Funlastic could decompose in less than 5 years. The capsules needed for 1 gram of plastic are about 8 capsules with a release period of 3-10 days. The advantages of LDPE plastic remain with FunLastic, this plastic can still be used at any time and with a large capacity. Through this approach, it is hoped that a more beautiful and sustainable future can be created by presenting realistic, innovative solutions.

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